

OBSERVATIONS OF THE HAARP EMISSION AT THE FAR SPATIALLY SEPARATED POSITIONS DURING THE HEATING CAMPAIGNS OF AUGUST 2024 AND JANUARY 2025 (PRELIMINARY RESULTS)

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The ionosphere can be imagined as a huge plasma laboratory of global scale. The conditions in such a laboratory cannot be reproduced in ground-based laboratories. Therefore, experiments in the ionosphere provide unique information for the physics of plasma and geospace. Interaction between electromagnetic waves and ionospheric plasma is studied using special powerful heating facilities. Currently, the heater of the High Frequency Active Auroral Research Program (HAARP) located at Gacon, Alaska is the most powerful among them.

The paper aims to investigate the mechanisms of propagation of HF radiation from the HAARP heating facility on radio paths of different lengths and orientations, as well as to find the effects of modified ionosphere region on propagation of HF signals. We are grateful to the organizers of the measuring campaigns with HAARP heating facility held from 13 to 21 August 2024 and from January 28 to February 02, 2025 for inviting us to take part in them.

Our main measuring tools in those heating campaigns were network of spatially separated internet-controlled Doppler HF receivers of the Institute of Radio Astronomy of the National Academy of Sciences of Ukraine (IRA NASU). Receiving sites are located in the Arctic (Tromso, Norway; Longyearbyen, Svalbard Island), Antarctica (at the Ukrainian Antarctic Akademik Vernadsky station (UAS)), Ukraine (Kharkiv), and Poland (LOFAR PL610 observatory in Borowiec). Thus, propagation conditions and ionospheric effects were investigated both on the meridional long-distance radio path HAARP-UAS (path length 15 640 km), and on shorter paths such as HAARP-Svalbard (4 326 km), HAARP-Tromso (5 275 km), HAARP-Kharkiv (7 500 km), HAARP-PL610 (7 170 km). The signals from CHU (Ottawa, Canada) precise time and frequency service station on carrier frequency of 7.85 MHz were registered at all receiving points to provide additional information about propagation conditions for the time of the experiments. Signal records from all receiving sites were processed, spectra and spectrograms were plotted. The time intervals when the heating signal was simultaneously registered at several or all sites are analyzed comprehensively. Possible manifestations of the non-linear effects of ionosphere modification by powerful radiation from the HAARP heating facility were also noted and analyzed.